

Consequences of Diabetes on Complications of Preterm Premature Rupture of Membrane

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Abstract:

Background: Diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes are complications that may be associated with preterm premature rupture of membrane (i.e. PPRM) during pregnancy. We have investigated the impact of gestational and overt diabetes on PPRM through a statistical campaign.

Methods: This study was conducted in two parts: In the first part, the PPRM patients (211 cases) were classified into three groups, without diabetes (W/ODM=126 cases), gestational diabetes (GDM=69 cases consist of 44 cases under insulin therapy and 25 cases of diet controlled), and diabetes mellitus (ODM=16 cases). PPRM complications were studied and compared between these three groups. In the second part, GDM patients under insulin therapy or diet control were compared to W/ODM patients in terms of PPRM complications.

Results: There were no significant statistical differences between the groups regarding pregnancy outcomes, except for mean gestational age at rupture of membrane and delivery. For maternal outcomes, there were significant changes between groups in terms of labor duration, hospital stay after childbirth, and severe preeclampsia. Fetus and neonatal outcomes suggested that the newborn weight, neonatal hyperglycemia, Apgar score, revive need, infant death, and umbilical cord blood gas test results (except BE) were significantly different between the three groups. Results of the second part of the study, in terms of statistically significant differences between insulin therapy, diet control, and W/ODM are consistent with the first part, for all discussed factors.

Conclusion: Results revealed that PPRM protocol management on PPRM cases who have gestational or overt diabetes is applicable and does not have any further risk.

Keywords: Diabetes, Premature Rupture Of The Membrane (PPROM), Insulin Therapy, Gestational Diabetes.

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Introduction

Preterm premature rupture of membrane takes place in upto three percent of pregnancies, which accounts for 35 percent of all preterm births [1]. The pathogenesis and leading causes of PPRM (i.e. spontaneous rupture of membrane before 37 weeks of pregnancy and before labor) are not completely understood. PPRM likely has various causes but intrauterine infection is believed by many to be a major predisposing event [1,2]. Intrauterine infection activates the matrix metalloproteinases by creating an inflammatory environment that disrupts membrane strength and leads to membrane rupture [3]. In addition to prematurity which is one of the most important causes of infant mortality, PPRM increases the risk of maternal complications such as chorioamnionitis, placental abruption, high rate of cesarean section (C/S), increasing hospital stay, postpartum Hemorrhage, etc.

As a result, pregnancies complicated by PPRM are associated with significant neonatal and maternal mortality and morbidity, with high immediate and long-term costs. Diabetes is the most common medical complication of pregnancy. Of all pregnancies, 9 to 10 percent are involved with diabetes [4]. Approximately 1-2 percent of women had overt diabetes before their pregnancy and 3-21 percent of pregnant women were diagnosed with gestational diabetes (GDM) during their pregnancy [5]. Diabetes prevalence in Iran is approximately 6% of pregnancies [6–8]. Complicated pregnancy with diabetes either overt diabetes (ODM) or gestational diabetes (GDM) seriously endangers the embryo, fetus, and mother's health [9,10]. Some fetal and neonatal complications are as follows: increasing chance of preterm birth (either preterm labor and PPRM or indicated preterm birth) [11], macro-

somnia [12– 14], hypoglycaemia [15], cardiomyopathy [16], etc. Diabetes also is problematic for mothers such that maternal welfare can be seriously jeopardized by increasing infection risk [17], caesarean rate [18– 20], and pregnancy-induced hypertension (HTN) [18,21]. In addition, a significant increase in type 2 diabetes is expected in women with GDM. It is estimated that half of these women will develop diabetes over the next 20 years [22,23].

Aims of this study are to study the impact of being diabetic and the variation of diabetes control approaches in PPRM cases through an extensive statistical campaign. We proposed to revisit many criteria related to both PPRM and diabetic pregnant women and to study the risk factors and outcomes.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted at Obstetrics and Gynaecology department of Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar from 1 July 2022 to 31 June 2023. All pregnant women who were hospitalized between 24 and 34 weeks of pregnancy in SKMCH in this period were included in this study. In this period all diabetic (ODM or GDM) pregnant women who have been admitted with PPRM diagnosis and without exclusion criteria were selected for the study. Due to the increasing diabetes prevalence, screening gestational diabetes is performed by OGTT 75 gm GLC test for all pregnant women at gestation age between 24 and 28 weeks.

For the control group, an estimated sample size of 126 PPRM cases who were without diabetes were selected and compared in terms of maternal and neonatal consequences. Exclusion criteria from the study were multiple pregnancies, congenital anomalies, placental complications, fetal growth restriction and polyhydramnios.

The patients were classified into three groups, without diabetes (W/ODM): 126 cases, gestational diabetes (GDM): 69 cases which consist of 44 cases with insulin therapy and 25 cases with diet controlled and overt diabetes (ODM): 16 cases all with

insulin therapy. The patients' information was kept confidential. In this study, the investigated baseline maternal characteristics are the patient's age, BMI, gravidity and history of premature delivery. The analyzed maternal factors in the study are: mean gestational age at rupture of membrane, latent hours between PPRM and labor onset, mean gestational age at delivery, labor duration, and hospital stay after childbirth, blood transfusion, severe preeclampsia and chorioamnionitis. Fetal and neonatal analyzed factors are newborn's weight, Apgar score, umbilical cord blood gas (ABG) test results, reviving newborns, infant death, respiratory distress, hypoglycemia, jaundice and neonatal infection. Also, the possibility of emergency caesarean section (C/S) and other kinds of delivery (e.g. natural vaginal delivery and surgical delivery) were studied. For a more detailed study of diabetes severity and the effect of insulin and diet control on PPRM gravidas, we investigated the maternal and neonatal complications in two subgroups of GDM (consisting of diet and insulin controlled).

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 20. The normality of continuous variables was tested using the One-Sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's test was used for normal distributions to compare the quantitative variables. Meanwhile, for abnormal distributions, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used. Categorical variables were compared by chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate. The significant level was $P < 0.05$.

Results

Baseline characteristics of study subjects are shown in Table 1. It could be observed that for both GDM and ODM groups, the mean age and body mass index (BMI) of mothers were significantly higher than the W/ODM group ($P = 0.003$ and 0.004 respectively). As shown, no statistical differences were observed regarding gravidity and history of preterm delivery between the three groups ($P > 0.05$). However, the prevalence history of preterm delivery for both GDM and ODM is about $(0.2/0.08=2.5)$ 2.5 times higher than W/ODM women.

Table 1: Baseline maternal characteristic in three study groups

	Age	BMI (kg/m ²)	Gravid	History of preterm delivery
W/ODM	29.5 ± 7.5	28.2 ± 4.2	2.2 ± 1.5	0.08 ± 0.5
GDM	33.0 ± 5.4	30.1 ± 3.2	2.4 ± 1.2	0.2 ± 0.4
ODM	30.6 ± 5.3	31.2 ± 6.4	2.7 ± 7.5	0.2 ± 0.3
Total	30.7 ± 6.9	28.9 ± 4.2	2.3 ± 1.4	0.1 ± 0.4
P-value	0.003	0.004	0.23	0.22

As shown in Table 2, both mean gestational age at PPRM onset and delivery in W/ODM were less than two other diabetic groups ($P = 0.04$). However, no significant statistical difference was found between the three groups in terms of latency period between PPRM and labor onset &/or delivery ($P = 0.12$).

Table 2: Primarily pregnancy outcomes between W/ODM, GDM, and ODM

	W/ODM	GDM	ODM	P-value
Mean gestational age at PPRM onset	30.8 ± 3.3	32.1 ± 2.3	31.4 ± 3.9	0.047
Mean gestational age at delivery	31.3 ± 3.3	32.4 ± 2.0	31.6 ± 3.9	0.04
Latency hours*	91.6	56.9	18.6	0.12

* Between PPRM and labor onset or C/S delivery

The same results were obtained between GDM with diet control and insulin therapy (Table 3). For latency hours, no considerable difference has been shown between the three groups and the average gestational age at PPRM and delivery was significantly higher in W/ODM (P = 0.04).

Table 3: Pregnancy outcomes between W/ODM, diet control, and insulin therapy

	W/ODM	Diet control	Insulin therapy	P-value
Mean gestational age at PPRM onset	30.8 ± 3.3	32.1 ± 2.5	32.1 ± 2.3	0.01
Mean gestational age at delivery	31.31 ± 3.3	32.46 ± 2.2	32.43 ± 1.9	0.04
Latency hours*	91.6	51	60.2	0.4

* Between PPRM and labor onset or C/S delivery

The reasons for pregnancy termination are shown in Table 4. According to this table, the most common reasons for pregnancy termination are preterm labor (PTL) and the end of 34 weeks, which were not significantly different among the three groups

(P = 0.9 and P = 0.3, respectively). However, the W/ODM group had significantly higher indicated termination cases than ODM and GDM patients (P = 0.03). For the indicated termination, fetal distress is the most common reason among others.

Table 4: Pregnancy termination reasons between ODM, GDM, and W/ODM groups

Cause	W/ODM No (%)	GDM No (%)	ODM No (%)	p-value
End of 34 week	46 (37)	32 (46)	8 (50)	0.3
PTL	59 (47)	34 (49)	7 (44)	0.91
Indicated termination	21 (17)	3 (4)	1 (6)	0.03
total number	126	69	16	-

In this study, in terms of delivery methods, Table 4 showed that the prevalence of cesarean section (C/S) and vaginal delivery (NVD) cases were not significantly different between all groups (P > 0.05). Also, no considerable difference was observed for the emergency C/S among the three groups (P = 0.17). Moreover, Table 5 demonstrated that the total C/S and NVD cases are 117 (55%) and 94 (45%), respectively. Thus, the average ce-

sarean section cases were about 1.2 times higher than vaginal delivery cases. Cesarean section surgery reasons are presented in Table 6 between ODM, GDM, and W/ODM groups. The childbirth methods for GDM subgroups of diet control and insulin therapy, Table 7 are the same as Table 5. Thus, there are no significant changes for childbirth methods between the subgroups and the control group.

Table 5: Delivery method of ODM, GDM and W/ODM groups

	W/ODM (%)	GDM (%)	ODM (%)	P-value
Emergency C/S	40 (62)	14 (33)	6 (60)	0.17
Total C/S section	65 (52)	42 (61)	10 (62.5)	0.39
Total NVD	61 (48)	27 (39)	6 (37.5)	0.39
Total cases	126	69	16	

Table 6: Summary of the reasons for having cesarean section surgery between ODM, GDM, and W/ODM groups

Cause	W/ODM No (%)	GDM No (%)	ODM No (%)
The history of C/S section	25 (38.5)	28 (66.7)	4 (40)
Meconium	3 (4.6)	4 (9.5)	0 (0)
Cardiotocographic abnormalities	20 (30.8)	4 (9.5)	2 (20)
Placental abruption	2 (3.1)	1 (2.4)	0 (0)
Malpresentation	11 (16.9)	4 (9.5)	3 (30)
Failure of induction	3 (4.6)	1 (2.4)	0 (0)
Severe preeclampsia	1 (1)	1 (2.4)	3 (30)
Umbilical cord prolapse	1 (1.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Total C/S section	65	42	10

Table 7: Delivery method of diet control, insulin therapy and W/ODM groups

	W/ODM (%)	Diet control (%)	Insulin therapy (%)	P-value
Emergency C/S	40 (32)	4 (16)	10 (23)	0.19
Total C/S section	65 (52)	14 (56)	28 (64)	0.39
Total NVD	61 (48)	11 (44)	16 (36)	0.39
Total cases	126	25	44	

Table 8 shows maternal outcomes among PPRM patients. Based on the results of the statistical tests, there were no significant differences between the three groups in terms of blood transfusion ($P = 0.96$) and chorioamnionitis in labor cases ($P = 0.77$).

However, the W/ODM and GDM group had a significantly lower rate of severe preeclampsia than

ODM patients ($P = 0.002$). There was a considerable statistical difference between the groups in terms of NVD labor duration ($P = 0.004$).

This difference was significant between the W/ODM and both diabetic groups. While the hospital stay after childbirth is significantly higher in diabetic groups compared to the W/ODM group ($P < 0.001$).

Table 8: Maternal outcomes

	W/ODM No (%)	GDM No (%)	ODM No (%)	P-value
Blood transfusion	6 (4.8)	8 (11.6)	2 (12.5)	0.96
NVD labor duration	4.7	3.2	1.5	0.004
Severe preeclampsia	1 (1)	1 (3)	3 (19)	0.00
Chorioamnionitis	3 (2.4)	1 (1.4)	0 (0)	0.77
Hospital stay period after childbirth	1.1 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 0.8	1.7 ± 0.6	0.00

The primary neonatal outcomes are summarized in Table 9. Neonates from the GDM and ODM groups had a significantly higher birth weight ($P < 0.001$) than the control group. The average fifth Apgar was significantly higher (about 20%) in GDM than in the two other groups ($P < 0.001$). Need to revive

newborns cases were significantly lower in GDM, as well as the ODM than W/ODM cases ($P < 0.001$). The umbilical cord blood gas pH was significantly lower in the ODM group than the other groups, while for BE, the ODM had the largest average amount.

Table 9: Primarily fetus and neonatal outcomes

	W/ODM	GDM	ODM	P-value
Newborn weight (gr)	1870.8	2417.4	2157.5	0.00
The mean Apgar score of the fifth minute	8.1 ± 2.8	9.5 ± 0.9	8.1 ± 2.9	0.00
Need to revive newborns	80 (63.5%)	11 (15.9%)	2 (12.5%)	0.00
BE *	no data	6.3 ± 2.8	10 ± 0.0	0.22
PH *	7.3 ± 0.1	7.3 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.1	0.02
HCO ³ (mE/L)*	19.8 ± 4.1	21.2 ± 3.9	21.8 ± 4.5	0.07
PCO ² (mmHg)*	39.4 ± 10.1	44.1 ± 13.2	58.0 ± 18.6	0.00

* Umbilical cord gas test results

Table 9 shows secondary fetal and neonatal outcomes. Hypoglycemia and infant death are both statistically different between the three groups.

The ODM group had significantly higher hypoglycemia cases ($P < 0.001$) compared to W/ODM and GDM. There was a statistically considerable difference in terms of infant death cases between GDM

and two other groups, with $P = 0.008$. For all cases the most common cause of infant death was pre-term birth.

According to Table 10, the three groups were not statistically different in terms of respiratory distress ($P = 0.59$) and infection ($P = 0.65$) as well as neonatal jaundice ($P = 0.8$).

Table 10: Secondary fetus and neonatal outcomes

	W/ODM	GDM	ODM	P-value
Respiratory distress	85 (67.5%)	48 (69.6%)	10 (62.5%)	0.59
Hypoglycemia	0 (0%)	3 (4.3%)	3 (18.8%)	0.00
Infant death	16 (12.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (12.5%)	0.008
Neonatal jaundice	72 (57.2%)	36 (52.2%)	9 (56.3%)	0.801
Infection	53 (42.1%)	33 (47.8%)	6 (37.5%)	0.653

The maternal and neonatal outcomes for the GDM subgroups (i.e. diet and insulin therapy) and control group are summarized in Table 11. From this table, it could be concluded that the results between the two subgroups of insulin therapy and diet control are the same as the three general groups (ODM, GDM, and W/ODM).

Therefore, as also shown in Table 11 the maternal and neonatal outcomes with statistically significant differences are: mean gestational age at delivery ($P = 0.04$), newborn weight ($P = 0.00$), need to revive

newborns ($P = 0.00$), and infant death ($P = 0.01$). The mean gestational age at delivery in the W/ODM group is significantly lower than diet and insulin groups. Neonates from the insulin therapy group had a significantly higher newborn weight compared to other groups.

The average birth weight in the insulin group is about 530 gr and 110 gr higher than W/ODM and diet group respectively. The W/ODM group has significantly the highest need to revive and infant death cases.

Table 11: Maternal and neonatal outcomes of diet control, insulin therapy, and W/ODM groups

Outcomes	W/ODM	Diet control	Insulin therapy	P-value
Mean gestational age at delivery	31.31 ± 3.3	32.46±2.2	32.43±1.9	0.04
PTL	59 (47)	14 (56%)	20 (45.5%)	0.67
Chorioamnionitis	3 (2.4)	0 (0%)	1 (2.3%)	0.74
Severe preeclampsia	1 (0.8%)	0 (0%)	1 (2.3%)	0.61
Newborn weight (gr)	1870.8±662.4	2291.2±638	2489.1±727.1	0.00
Need to revive newborns	80 (63.5%)	5 (20%)	8 (18.2%)	0.00
Infant death	16 (12.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (4.5%)	0.01
PH	7.32 ± 0.10	7.31 ± 0.09	7.28 ± 0.11	0.14
Neonatal jaundice	72 (57.1%)	14 (56%)	22 (50%)	0.72
Infection	53 (42.1%)	11 (44%)	22 (50%)	0.66
Respiratory distress	85 (67.5%)	18 (72%)	30 (68.2%)	0.91

Discussion

In our study, the most common reasons for pregnancy termination in every group were preterm labor and reaching the end of 34 weeks of pregnancy. The latency period and the incidence of chorioamnionitis were not different between ODM, GDM and W/ODM groups. The only considerable difference in terms of pregnancy termination was the indicated termination in which fetal distress was the most common reason. The significant difference in indicated termination between groups may be due to the greater number of control group cases.

The same results were observed for the GDM subgroups (i.e. insulin and diet control). These results demonstrate that the expectant management of PPRM until the end of 34 weeks in both diabetic groups has not increased the maternal infection and the risk of preterm labor, compared to non-diabetic gravidas. Yogev [35] showed that the rate of spontaneous preterm birth in GDM does not increase compared to patients without GDM, but achieving established glycemic control levels may reduce the rate of spontaneous preterm birth in GDM. Their results are consistent with our results, as the emergency C/S is lower for GDM compared to the control group. Sheiner et al., (26), Torres (27), and Kessous et al., (28) demonstrated that the ODM in PPRM cases has an increased risk of chorioamnionitis in parallel with the increased risk of other infections; whereas Kari et al., [25] observed no significant relationship between maternal chori-

oamnionitis and PPRM occurrence in the diabetic patients rather than the women in the nondiabetic group. The results from our study are consistent with those obtained by Kari et al., [25] in terms of the relationship between PPRM and diabetes and the occurrence of maternal infection.

As shown, for all groups, the rate of C/S was more than NVD, but there was no considerable difference between the three groups regarding overall C/S and emergency C/S prevalence. We found that the cesarean delivery for PPRM cases is 50% more common in pregnant women with GDM or ODM than nondiabetic women. Previous studies have also shown that the risk of cesarean section is higher (about 30% to 35%) among diabetics than W/ODM patients [13,14,29]. Diabetes alone is not an indication for C/S before 38 weeks of gestation, it becomes evident that C/S may be the preferred choice for many obstetricians due to the various maternal and fetal complications associated with diabetes (30).

The interesting point about our study is the long labor duration (active phase of labor) in W/ODM groups. The newborn weight and gestational age were both higher in GDM and ODM groups, but the labor duration was higher in the W/ODM group. Although it is impossible to get an accurate conclusion because of the small number of VD cases, we could approximately explain this result as follows: 1) the smaller size of neonates of W/ODM may cause lower head compression pressure on the cervix which can make the active phase of labor

longer 2) another possible reason is that because of the lower gestational age of the control group; the existing number of oxytocin receptors are less than both diabetic groups.

The results suggested, for maternal outcomes, one of the significant differences among the groups was the shorter stay duration of W/ODM mothers after delivery, which was consistent with the Kari et al., [25]. ODM group has the highest hospital stay of all other groups. Also, severe preeclampsia was found significantly higher in ODM groups compared to others. Wen et al., (31) demonstrated that preeclampsia is associated with a longer postoperative length of stay during delivery hospitalizations. Thus, in our study, the mean longer hospital stay for ODM might be due to the higher preeclampsia cases in this group. Another reason that could explain the longer hospital stay for ODM is the longer time needed to control the serum blood glucose after delivery and changing the insulin to the oral anti-glycemic agent.

As is shown in the result part, the considerable differences in neonatal outcomes were lower birth weight, lower fifth Apgar score, higher rate of reviving neonates, and more infantile death in the W/ODM group which all could be explained by the less gestational age at delivery of this group. The rate of neonatal respiratory distress was not significantly different between the three groups. However, Kari et al., [25] reported that the gestational age at delivery, Apgar score, need to revive newborn, fetal distress, and NICU admission were not significantly different between the three groups. When we compared the mentioned neonatal outcomes between subgroups of the GDM and the W/ODM group, we reached the same results. Therefore, it seems that the only leading cause of significant differences in neonatal outcomes is the less gestational age at delivery of the W/ODM group.

Regarding neonatal infections in PPRM cases, unlike Hollingsworth et al., (32), our results indicated that there is no significant relationship between neonatal infection and PPRM occurrence in diabetic women rather the women in the control group. In our study, the rate of neonatal hypoglycemia was considerably higher in the groups with GDM and ODM compared to the diabetes-free group. Consistent with our study, Magee et al., (33), Boriboonthirunsarn et al., [20], implied that hypoglycemia is the most prevalent neonatal complication related to maternal diabetes. However, Kari et al., [25] reported in their study that the relationship between diabetes and hypoglycemia was only found in ODM rather than GDM. The umbilical cord blood gas test results showed significantly lower pH levels with high base excess and PCO₂ for neonates of the ODM group. This mixed metabolic mild acidosis could be due to chronic stress in the uterine environment of the fetal life of these

cases. This chronic stress as Aalipour et al., (34) showed in their study could be due to pre-existing hyperinsulinemia and hypoglycaemia in the uterine environment because of pregestational maternal diabetes.

In the second part of this study, the influences of diet and insulin therapy on neonatal and maternal consequences of PPRM cases were studied. Previous studies highlighted the fact that insulin therapy, effective treatment regimens consisting of diet and exercise are beneficial approaches for the well-being of mothers, the growing fetus and the newborn health (35). However, little is known about the effects of diabetes therapy approaches on PPRM cases. It is interesting to note that our results in the second part of the study confirm the first part.

Conclusion

The strengths of our study are the big size of PPRM patients conducted for the first time, and about 20 different maternal and neonatal study factors. The effects of gestational/mellitus diabetes and PPRM on the occurrence of maternal/neonatal sequelae were separately compared in this study. More importantly, the effect of the different types of GDM management (i.e. insulin and diet-controlled) on PPRM maternal and neonatal consequences were studied.

Our study demonstrates that conducting PPRM protocol management on PPRM cases who have gestational or overt diabetes do not have any further risk on maternal and neonatal consequences. Due to the retrospective nature of this study, unfortunately, the past ODM patients' records were incomplete, and also the diabetes severity based on HbA_{1C} and FBS average was not available, accordingly the comparison of PPRM complications was not possible.

Therefore, in further prospective studies, it is necessary to compare the complications of PPRM in ODM patients with diabetes type I and type II. Also, studies with larger sample sizes especially with more overt diabetic patients which could be matched in terms of baseline characteristics and the gestational age of PPRM onset must be designed to assess maternal and neonatal complications and to evaluate long-term follow-up of mothers and children. However, it seems that until then, there is no need to change the PPRM management protocol for diabetic gravidas.

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